

NOTES

Studies on Molecular Adducts of Hydroxyphenyltelluriumtrichloride

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THE interaction of aryltellurium trihalides with various bases has been studied¹⁻⁴. We now report some new molecular adducts of hydroxyphenyltellurium trichloride of the general formula $p\text{-HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{TeCl}_3 \cdot L$ [$L = 2\text{-picoline}$ ($\alpha\text{-pic}$), 3-picoline ($\beta\text{-pic}$), 4-picoline ($\gamma\text{-pic}$), $2,2'\text{-bipyridyl}$ (bipy), $1,10\text{-phenanthroline}$ (phen), pyridine (Py), imidazole (Idz), benzimidazole (Bdz), triethylamine (Tea), triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO), triphenylarsine oxide (TPAsO), dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), dimethyl formamide (DMF), $4\text{-picoline-N-oxide}$ ($\gamma\text{-picO}$)].

Experimental

Hydroxyphenyltellurium trichloride was prepared by the reported method⁵. All the Lewis bases were obtained from B.D.H. and were used after purification by conventional methods. TGA was recorded on a thermogravimetric balance supplied by Fertilizer Corporation of India. The physico chemical measurements were made as reported earlier⁶.

Preparation of the adducts :

The complexes were prepared by adding the Lewis base (5 mmole) in dry methanol (10 ml) to $p\text{-hydroxyphenyltellurium trichloride}$ (5 mmole) in the same solvent (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2-3 hr. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the residual solution was kept overnight in a freeze to yield a crystalline product. In some cases, the product was isolated by addition of an excess of diethyl ether. The products were washed with the same solvent and dried *in vacuo*.

Results and Discussion

The data presented in Table 1 indicate 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. They are sharp melting crystalline solids insoluble in common organic solvents and are insensitive to atmospheric oxygen and moisture. Molar conductance values of $10^{-3} M$ solution lie in the range $20\text{-}30 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in nitrobenzene suggesting 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour of the adducts². The observed

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR MOLECULAR ADDUCTS OF HYDROXYPHENYLTELLURIUM TRICHLORIDE

Ligand	m.p. (°C)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				
		C	H	N	Te	OI
$\alpha\text{-pic}$	117	84.00 (84.80)	2.78 (2.87)	3.98 (3.93)	29.92 (30.36)	25.72 (25.31)
$\beta\text{-pic}$	180	84.00 (84.80)	2.78 (2.87)	3.98 (3.93)	29.92 (30.36)	25.72 (25.31)
$\gamma\text{-pic}$	165	84.00 (84.80)	2.78 (2.87)	3.98 (3.93)	29.92 (30.36)	25.72 (25.31)
bipy	68	88.12 (87.59)	2.40 (2.47)	5.88 (6.26)	28.99 (28.58)	22.09 (23.01)
Py	232	81.98 (82.52)	2.78 (2.48)	8.40 (8.44)	31.88 (31.41)	25.92 (26.18)
phen	198	48.00 (42.61)	2.72 (2.58)	6.28 (5.52)	25.18 (25.15)	20.90 (20.96)
Tea	286	84.45 (88.65)	4.80 (4.70)	8.98 (8.27)	84.00 (29.79)	25.81 (24.88)
Bdz	95	86.72 (85.07)	2.55 (2.49)	6.99 (6.29)	29.00 (28.66)	24.89 (23.89)
Idz	208	87.70 (87.85)	2.40 (2.29)	7.71 (7.09)	82.20 (82.29)	26.68 (26.91)
TPPO*	189	47.60 (47.61)	3.88 (3.93)	—	21.10 (21.07)	17.40 (17.56)
TPAsO*	149	45.01 (44.39)	3.22 (3.10)	—	19.64 (19.65)	16.48 (16.88)
$\gamma\text{-picO}$	190	82.95 (83.04)	2.43 (2.77)	8.30 (8.21)	28.95 (29.25)	24.00 (24.88)
DMSO	150	23.40 (23.71)	2.32 (2.78)	—	31.40 (31.49)	26.17 (26.24)
DMF	100	28.09 (27.01)	3.32 (3.02)	3.58 (3.50)	31.73 (31.88)	26.89 (26.57)

* TPPO—Conductivity (nitrobenzene) 21.45 ; molecular weight (nitrobenzene) 290.4 (605.3).

TPAsO—Conductivity (nitrobenzene) 24.50 ; molecular weight (nitrobenzene) 307.4 (649.3).

molecular weight of the compounds (in nitrobenzene) is approximately half of the calculated molecular weight which indicates their dissociation into two ions in solution.

IR spectra : IR spectra of the adducts were recorded in the region $4000\text{-}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. A critical comparison of the spectra of the free ligands with those of the corresponding adducts have been made (Table 2).

Nitrogen donors : A negative shift in $\nu\text{C-N}$ of aliphatic amines is indicative of coordination from the nitrogen atom⁷. The absorption due to $\nu\text{C=N}$ (at $1569 \pm 18 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in free Py, $\alpha\text{-}$, $\beta\text{-}$ or $\gamma\text{-pic}^{8-9}$, bipy¹⁰ or phen¹¹ undergoes a positive shift on coordination. The corresponding absorption in Bdz and Idz appears at 1630 and 1595 cm^{-1} , respectively which undergoes a negative shift indicating donation from the tertiary nitrogen atom of the ligands^{12,13}.

Oxygen donors : The $\nu\text{N-O}$ in $\gamma\text{-pico}$, $\nu\text{C-O}$ in DMF, $\nu\text{S-O}$ in DMSO, $\nu\text{P-O}$ in TPPO and

TABLE 2—INFRARED DATA OF THE ADDUCTS OF HYDROXYPHENYLTELLURIUM TRICHLORIDE

Ligand	Interacting group	Stretching frequency (cm ⁻¹)	
		Pure ligand	Adduct
α -pic	-C=N	1574 s	1630 s
β -pic	-C=N	1576 s	1638 s
γ -pic	-C=N	1578 s	1640 s
bipy	-C=N	1560 s	1580 sh
Py	-C=N	1583 s	1640 m
phen	-C=N	1578 s	1595 m
Tea*	-C=N	1170 s	1145 sbr
Bds	-C=N	1630 m	1620 m
Ids	-C=N	1595 s	1580 s
TPPO	-P=O	1195 vs	1120 vs
TPAsO	-As=O	880 s	825 s
γ -picO	-N=O	1250 vs	1210 vs
DMSO	-S=O	1045 vs	980 vs
DMF	-C=O	1666 vs	1640 vs

* $\nu_{\text{sym}}(-\text{C}-\text{N})$ in Tea :at 830 cm⁻¹ undergoes negative shift and appears at 809 cm⁻¹.

$\nu_{\text{As}-\text{O}}$ in TPAsO undergo a negative shift in the complexes which suggests that these ligands are bonded to tellurium through the oxygen atom. This is also supported by a slight positive shift of $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ in DMSO and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}}$ (contiguous to alkyl) in DMF¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

TGA measurements on a few representative adducts $p-\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{TeCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}$ (L=Py, bipy, γ -picO, DMSO) indicate slow continuous decomposition in the temperature range 120-600°, yielding a residue of Te metal. Unstable intermediates could not be identified.

The coordination number of the adducts in case of monodentate bases is limited to five while for bidentate ligands it is six.

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cis-Diacido Complexes of Pd(II) and Pt(II) with Pyrrolidine

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COMPLEXES of Pd(II) and Pt(II) have been studied extensively¹⁻⁴ and are still of current interest due to their physiological properties and anti-cancer activity⁵. In the present note we are reporting the *cis*-diacido complexes of Pd(II) and Pt(II) with pyrrolidine (pyr).

Experimental

The ligand was obtained from Suchhardt (Germany) and palladium(II) chloride and chloroplatinic acid were obtained from Johnson-Mathey (London). Platinum(II) chloride was prepared by reducing H₂PtCl₆ by hydrazine hydrochloride⁶.

Preparation of the complexes :

[M(pyr)₂Cl₂] (M=Pd or Pt) : An aqueous acidic solution of metal chloride (pH 2-4) was treated with an excess of ligand with stirring till pH rose to 4-5. Palladium(II) complexes separated immediately while platinum(II) complexes separated on concentration and cooling to room temp. The products were collected, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.

[M(pyr)₂X₂] (M=Pd or Pt; X=Br, I, NO₂ or NCS) : An aqueous suspension of [M(pyr)₂Cl₂] (0.5 g in ~30 ml) was refluxed with an excess of sodium or potassium salt of the appropriate anion on a steam bath for 1 to 2 hr. Pd(II) complexes separated on cooling, while Pt(II) complexes were obtained on concentrating and cooling the refluxate to room temp. The products were collected and dried as above.

The results of elemental analysis are given in Table 1. The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was determined by Gouy method. The IR spectra of the complexes were recorded as KBr disc in the 4000-625 cm⁻¹ range at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and electronic reflectance spectra in